

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

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ABSTRACT: An on-farm trial (OFT) for three years (2022-23, 2023-24, and 2024-25) was conducted by ICAR-ANGRAU, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Kondempudi directly in farmers' fields of five selected villages, viz., Sirsapalli, Neelumputu, Mattijooru, Aruku, and Dumbriguda, in the tribal agency of the Alluri Sitaram Raj district of Andhra Pradesh to assess the performance of two promising gladiolus varieties, viz., Arka Amar and Arka Aayush, with regard to yield and economic analysis against the farmers' practice variety, Arka Pratham. A total of twenty-five farmers actively participated in the OFT, covering an area of 6.5 acres. With regard to yield, Arka Amar proved to be the best, followed by Arka Aayush and Arka Pratham, with a pooled three-year spike yield of 183731.6, 169580.8, and 155936.6 spikes/ha, respectively. During the years of the trial, the days to spike emergence of Arka Pratham, Arka Amar and Arka Aayush were taken from 67.47, 76.33 and 78.47 days after planting, respectively. And also a pooled three-year number of corms per plant, the best in Arka amar (1.469), followed by Arka Aayush (1.356) and Arka Pratham (1.247). During the years of the trial, the spike yields of Arka Amar and Arka Aayush increased from 14.63% to 20.71% and 7.31% to 9.57%, respectively. Average cost-benefit ratios for the three years for Arka Amar, Arka Aayush, and Arka Pratham varieties were 1:2.75, 1:2.48, and 1:2.21, respectively. The extension gap was between 22500 and 32750 and 11250 and 14750 spikes/ha for Arka Amar and Arka Aayush, respectively. Results on the Technology Index ranged between 24.16 and 17.87, 18.48 and 14.59, and 20.21 and 17.94% for Arka Amar, Arka Aayush, and Arka Pratham (farmers' practice), respectively, and also revealed that for both the gladiolus varieties, there is much scope for demonstrated technology in the tribal agency areas of the Alluri Sitaramraj district of Andhra Pradesh.

KEYWORDS: Gladiolus, On-farm trials (OFT), Quality parameters, Spike length, vase life, spike yield, Extension Gap, Technology Gap, Technology Index, Demo plots and Cost of cultivation.

INTRODUCTION

Gladiolus (*Gladiolus grandiflora* L.) a member of the Iridaceae family is an important bulbous crop grown wide range of climatic conditions both plain and hill regions of India. It is also known as queen of the bulbous plants is very popular as a cut flower, both with the consumer and the florist alike because of its many spike forms, colors and color combinations, an advantage in every floral arrangement (Bushman 1990). It is also used as bouquets are esteemed during social gatherings where spikes of gladiolus in several attractive colors are used to honour dignitaries, welcome guests and wish the sick a swift recovery and among several other things (Ravinath 2007). It has a pivotal place as cut flower both in the domestic as well as international market (Pandey *et al.* 2012). Modern Gladiolus an important cut flower, considered to have been bred originally from only six species (Lewis *et al.* 1972). There are about 260 species of gladiolus (Singh and Sisodia 2017) till 2017. As India has such a diverse climate, it is ideal for cultivating a variety of flowers in gladiolus at tribal agency areas of Aruku and Paderu mandals of Alluri Sitaram Raj district due to it is having mild climatic conditions with altitude of 1500 MSL. Most of the tribal farmers of ASR district living on cultivation of farming and tourism. ASR district is also known for tourism it attract lakhs of tourists from different states and different countries in winter season every year. Introduction of Gladiolus as a new crop with good varieties of Arka Amar, Arka Aayush and Arka Pratham are very rich in varietal wealth and very attractive spike colours which are used and sale as cut flowers in market and also getting additional income through catching of tourism every year during winter season. In such way improve the tribal farmer's lively wood, social and economic status. Hence, varietal introduction and evaluation becomes necessary to find out suitable varieties in ASR district for the specific region (Kumar and Yadav 2005). Keeping these gaps in interest, an on-farm trial (OFT) was undertaken right in farmers' fields by ICAR- ANGRAU, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Kondempudi for evaluating the gladiolus suitable introduced varieties, growth and corm yield parameters, shelf life and cost of cultivation in tribal farmers fields and demonstrate along with other agronomic practices. Twenty-five participant farmers drawn from five villages viz. Sirsapalli, Neelumputu, Mattijooru, Aruku

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and Dumbriguda (5.0 acres field area with Arka Amar, Arka Aayush and Arka Pratham varieties) participated in the OFT for three consecutive years viz. 2022 - 23-2023-24 and 2024-25. Gladiolus bulbs are used for propagation (Bushman 1990)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The list of the participant farmers was prepared very meticulously based on the response and interest evinced in group meetings and interaction sessions with progressive farmers and scientists. The skill training in the demos focussed on the selection of quality of seeds, seed treatment, manures and fertilizer schedule and nutrient management, irrigation schedule, plant protection measures, and spikes harvesting at right stage and right time. Prior to commencing the on farm trial, Soil pH, electrical conductivity, and available potassium were determined by standard methods (Jackson, 1973). Available nitrogen and phosphorus were determined by alkaline permanganate method (Subbaiah and Asija, 1956) and colorimetric method (Bray and Kurtz, 1945), respectively. Gladiolus bulbs Arka Amar and Arka Aayush were selected for OFTs; those of the Arka Pratham variety were marked as the farmers' practice/reference check/local variety for assessing the yield and economic analysis. The selected gladiolus bulbs were seed treated with *Trichoderma viride* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* at 10 g/kg of seed for preventing soil-borne diseases. The spacing (45 cm x 25 cm) facilitated a greater number of bulbs for getting more numbers of gladiolus spikes. Seed treatment was done with @ 10 g *Trichoderma viride* and 10 g for 30 minutes against soil-borne pathogens and fungal and bacterial diseases, respectively. The fields received well-decomposed FYM @ 10 tonnes/acre at the last ploughing. N, P and K @ 20, 35 and 35 kg/acre were applied through commercial fertilizers. P was applied as a basal dose, while N was applied in two equal splits at the third leaf and sixth leaf stages. Plant protection measures included installation of blue and yellow sticky traps @ 4 to 6 /acre for observation of the sucking pest complex. Spraying of neem oil @ 5 ml/litre (10000 ppm) at 45 days after planting and 60 days after planting for control of insect egg masses. Plants were irrigated through a drip system. Harvesting of spikes was done at 2 numbers of florets that opened first at the base; it was the right time of harvesting spikes for extending shelf life. The harvesting of spikes was done at 5-day intervals. Performance and yields of Arka amar and Arka aayush were compared against Arka pratham (farmers' practice). The biometrical observations on various morphological parameters of vegetative growth, flowering and bulb production were recorded. The extension parameters such as Extension Gap, Technology Gap, and Technology Index were calculated by formulae suggested by Samui *et al.* (2000), Renbomo and Pijush Kanti (2016) and Kale *et al.*, (2020) to study the impact of front-line demonstrations over traditional practices by farmers.

$$1. \text{ Technology gap} = \text{Potential yield} - \text{Demonstrated yield}$$

$$2. \text{ Extension gap} = \text{Demonstrated yield} - \text{Yield under existing practice}$$

$$3. \text{ Technology Index} = \frac{(\text{Potential yield} - \text{Demonstrated yield}) \times 100}{\text{Potential yield}}$$

$$4. \text{ Per cent increase over farmers practices} = \frac{\text{Improved practices} - \text{Farmers practices}}{\text{farmers practices}} \times 100$$

$$5. \text{ Per cent increase yield} = \frac{\text{Demonstration yield} - \text{Farmer practice yield}}{100/\text{Farmer practice yield}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physicochemical properties of the soils viz. pH 6.78, electrical conductivity 0.05 dS m⁻¹, and available N, P and K at 168.46, 32.17 and 89.92 kg ha⁻¹ respectively, indicated the soils to be ideal for commercial cultivation of gladiolus. With respect to growth and yield attributes of Gladiolus as per Table 1 and Fig. 1 revealed that the plant height was increased substantially from 2022-23, 2023-24 and to 2024-25, in three years study. Among the three varieties, the highest plant height (113.93 cm) was recorded in Arka Amar, followed by Arka Aayush (86.95 cm) and Arka Pratham (79.88 cm) at 60 days after planting. The variations in plant growth among the varieties are due to the genetic character of individual genotypes. A similar result has been reported by Bharathi *et al.* (2023), Effat *et al.* (2018), Ritter *et al.* (2001), Ahmed *et al.* (2002), Azimi (2020) and Kirti kumara *et al.* (2023). As per Table 1 and Fig.2 revealed that the spike emergence maximum days were taken in Arka Aayush (78.47 days) followed by Arka Amar (76.33 days) and the early spike emergence was recorded in Arka pratham (67.47 days). The variation in spike emergence may be due to its varietal character and the corm vigor attributed because of the genetic potential of the varieties. These results are in accordance with the findings of Arfa *et al.* (2023), Nalage *et al.* (2019), Ghadage (2020), Pasannavar *et al.* (1998) Neeraj *et al.* (2000). Similarly, maximum spike length (113.45 cm) was observed in Arka amar followed by Arka aayush (106.96 cm) and Arka pratham (89.46 cm) as per table 2 and fig.4. Whereas the gladiolus spike vase life was highest noticed in Arka amar (11.48 days) followed by Arka Aayush (9.33 days) and Arka pratham (8.13 days) (Table 2 and Fig.6). The variations in spike length and gladiolus spike vase life might be due to variations in the availability of stored food material in the corms. Cultivars having corms with more

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stored food material produces longer spikes with maximum vase life of spikes. A similar results has been confirmatory with the findings of Mahaveer *et al.* (2013), Geeta *et al.* (2014), Rao and Sushma (2015) and Arfa *et al.* (2023), in gladiolus

The quantity of florets per spike significantly rose in all three treatments across the three years of study (Table 2 and fig.7). The highest maximum number of florets per spike (21.1) was observed in Arka Amar, followed by Arka Aayush (19.66), while the lowest number of florets per spike (17.94) was found in Arka Pratham. The variations in the number of florets per spike could be attributed to differences in the genetic composition of the various cultivars and their effective use of natural resources and inputs, in addition to the size of the planting material. Comparable findings were observed by Devi Priya (2014), Rao and Sushma (2015), Ghadage (2020), Shaukat *et al.* (2013), and Arfa *et al.* (2023) in gladiolus. Among the varieties, Arka Amar showed the greatest number of corms per plant (1.469), with Arka Aayush following at 1.356 and Arka Pratham at 1.247, as indicated in table 2 and fig. 8. The differences could be genetic; the potential of varieties leads to a range of phenotypic expressions. Varieties that generate a greater number of corms per plant can be regarded as effective multipliers and could serve as parental lines in future breeding programs, as indicated by Kadam *et al.* (2014). The corm propagation of gladiolus varieties using aeroponics was consistent with the findings of Lepcha *et al.* (2007), Hemlata (2019), Swaroop *et al.* (2019), and Kirti Kumar *et al.* (2023). These results closely aligned with the observations reported by Sankari *et al.* (2012), Singh *et al.* (2013) and Kadam *et al.* (2014) in gladiolus

Gladiolus spike yield (Number of spikes/ha) for the three treatments showed a significant increase from 2022-23 to 2023-24 and then to 2024-25 in a three-year study (Table 3 and Fig. 9). The significant rise in yield could be attributed to the differences in the sprouting percentage of corms, the number of sprouts per plant, and the vigor and diameter of bulbs, which are traits controlled by genetics. Comparable findings were noted by Nalage *et al.* (2019), Naresh *et al.* (2015) and Ghadage (2020) in gladiolus. The spike yield showed a significant increase across all three treatments during the three years from 2022-23, 2023-24, and 2024-25 (176250, 184070, and 190875 No of spikes/ha compared to 165000, 1708675, and 172875 No of spikes/ha for Arka amar and Arka aayush, respectively)

Percentage gains in spike yield compared to farmers' practices were 14.63, 18.04, and 20.71 for Arka Amar and 7.31, 9.57, and 10.21 for Arka Aayush in the years 2022-23, 2023-24, and 2024-25, respectively. The maximum count of corms/plants was noted in Arka Amar (1.469), succeeded by Arka Ayushh (1.356) and Arka Pratham (Table 3 and Fig 8). The rise in spike yield could be attributed to the maximum diameter of corms, their weight, and the count of corms per plant, which are crucial factors for generating the highest quantity of spikes with additional florets per corm. A comparable finding was documented by Lepcha *et al.* (2007), Swaroop (2005), Sankari *et al.* (2012), Singh *et al.* (2013), Kadam *et al.* (2014), Nalage *et al.* (2015), Naresh *et al.* (2015), and Ghadage (2020) in gladiolus cultivation

The Extension Gap with Arka Amar and Arka Aayush varied from 22500 to 32750 and 11250 to 14750 spikes/ha, respectively. The outcomes align with the results of the studies by Hiremath and Nagaraju (2010), Kale *et al.* (2020), Bhat *et al.* (2017), Manjunatha Rao *et al.* (2020), and Arfa *et al.* (2023). The rising adoption of cutting-edge production technologies combined with high-yielding varieties will reduce the extension gap. Consequently, there is a significant necessity to instruct farmers on choosing a high-yielding variety suitable for the region and embracing modern technology to bridge this extensive extension gap using various extension approaches, such as frontline demonstrations, cluster frontline demonstrations, Kisan melas, field days, and convergence meetings with relevant departments. These initiatives and programmes will undoubtedly encourage the farmers to abandon their traditional methods and embrace the new technology proposed by the visiting scientists.

Table 3 and fig 11 revealed that the technology gap consistently decreased in all three gladiolus varieties during the three years of study. The technology gap with Arka Amar and Arka Aayush ranged from 56172.4 to 41547.4 and 37412.5 to 29537.5 (Number of spikes/ha), respectively. The gap may be attributed to the variations in inherent soil fertility and weather conditions (Renbomo and Pijush Kanti, 2016) Kirti Kumar *et al.* (2023), Kadam *et al.* (2014) and Arfa *et al.* (2023). Variety-wise, location-specific trials and recommendations are required for minimising the technology gap in yield in different situations. The technology gap results revealed that the OFT farmers, after observing the high yields in the first year, enthusiastically implemented the package of practices of the demo plots in the subsequent two years. Similar findings were also recorded by Bhat *et al.* (2017), Kumar and Tadav (2005), Nair and Shiva (2003), Kale *et al.* (2020) and Singh *et al.* (2017).

There was a decrease in the Technology Index parameter from 2022-23 to 2024-25 (Table 2 and Fig. 7). The Technology Index for Arka Amar for 2022-23 and 2024-25 was 24.16 and 17.87, while the same for Arka Aayush for the years was 18.48 and 14.59, respectively (Table 3 and Fig.12). The lower the value of the Technology Index, the greater the feasibility of introducing a technology to reach a desired target. There is thus much scope for demonstrated technology in growing gladiolus in these tribal agency areas of the Alluri Sitaram Raj district of Andhra Pradesh for improving its yield. Similar results have earlier been reported by Renbomo and Pijush Kanti (2016), Kale *et al.* (2020), Katare *et al.* (2011), Keshava reddy *et al.* (2018) and Dayanand (2012), Kirti kumar *et al.* (2023). Kadam *et al.* (2014) and Swarop *et al.* (2019) in Gladiolus

Results on economic analysis parameters such as the cost of cultivation, gross return, net return and benefit-cost (B:C) ratio are depicted in Table 4 and Fig. 16. There was a drastically decreased the cost of cultivation second year onwards from 2023-24 and 2024-25. The cost of cultivation was highest in the first year (Rs.8, 24,625/ha) due to the high initial cost with respect to seed

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material; thereafter, the cost of cultivation was drastically reduced (69.5%) from the second year (2023-24) onwards to the third year of cultivation (2024-25) in all the treatments, which might be the first-year harvested gladiolus bulbs used as planting material in subsequent years. The cost of cultivation of Arka Amar, Arka Aayush and Arka Pratham ranged from Rs. 8, 24,625 in 2022-23 to Rs. 2, 48,637/ha in 2024-25. The net return is too high in Arka Amar during 2024-25 (Rs. 8, 93,868/ha), and the net returns are too low in farmer-practiced Arka Pratham during 2022-23 (Rs. 97,875/ha), followed by Arka Aayush (Rs. 1, 65,375/ha) and Arka Amar (Rs. 2, 32,875/ha), which might be due to the increasing cost of cultivation, mostly seed material cost. Net returns were higher in the demo plots in all three years of study (Table 4 and Fig. 15) over farmer practice. A similar result has been reported by Sankari *et al.* (2012), Singh *et al.* (2013), Kadam *et al.* (2014), Naresh *et al.* (2015) and Ghadage (2020). The results suggest that the cultivation of gladiolus using the recommended technology, exemplified by the varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the demonstrated plots of the study, will close the technology gap, help local gladiolus farmers attain higher yields, and greatly improve their economic status and quality of life. It is vital to highlight that the area's Krishi Vigyan Kendras and agricultural extension bodies must undertake this responsibility with honesty and dedication

CONCLUSION

High yielding, appealing, and long-lasting spike varieties along with enduring gladiolus varieties (Arka Amar and Arka Aayush) in the demo plots demonstrated significantly greater yields compared to farmers' practice (Arka Pratham). The demo plots had greater net returns and a higher benefit-cost ratio compared to the methods used by farmers. On-farm experiments conducted by researchers in collaboration with farmers showed the importance of new varieties, seed treatment, and the implementation of suggested best practices including proper timing and application of manures and fertilizers, bio-agents, irrigation, and timely harvesting of gladiolus spikes to achieve a high yield of gladiolus spikes. Gladiolus is a classic cut flower species that experiences significant demand in commerce and the marketplace. Gladiolus cultivators in the area, however, lack knowledge of scientific growing methods for gladiolus and are also reluctant to embrace new technology. With additional OFTs, farmers would be able to witness firsthand in their own fields the way technology can increase yields. A higher spike yield indicates increased profit and an improved economic situation for the tribal farmers

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Table 1. Growth and Yield attributes characters of Gladiolus (Var.) over farmers' practice.

Particulars	Plant height (cm) (60 DAP)				Days to spike emergence				Spike length (cm)			
	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pooled	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pooled	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pooled
T1: Farmers' practice – Arka pratham	78.5	81.4	79.74	79.88	67.45	65.72	69.24	67.47	88.5	90.25	89.65	89.46
T2: Arka Amar	110.7	114.4	116.7	113.93	74.85	76.52	77.63	76.33	109.4	117.52	113.45	113.45
T3: Arka Aayush	89	79.45	92.4	86.95	78.92	80.32	76.18	78.47	106.32	110.32	104.25	106.96

Table 2. Flowering and Quality parameters of Gladiolus (Var.) over farmers' practice.

Particulars	Gladiolus spike vase life (days)				Number of florets /spike				No of corms/plant			
	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pooled	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pooled	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pooled
T1: Farmers' practice – Arka pratham	7.5	8.25	7.85	7.867	16.18	18.36	19.28	17.94	1.23	1.247	1.265	1.247
T2: Arka Amar	11.48	10.37	11.24	11.03	18.28	21.15	23.87	21.1	1.41	1.47	1.527	1.469
T3: Arka Aayush	9.333	9.85	10.12	9.768	17.35	20.47	21.16	19.66	1.32	1.366	1.383	1.356

Table 3. Yield, Technology Gap, Extension Gap and Technology Index of gladiolus cultivation (Var.) over farmers' practice.

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Particulars	No of Spikes/ha					% Increase yield (No of Spikes/ ha) over farmers' practice			Technology Gap (No of Spikes/ha)			Extension Gap (No of Spikes/ha)			Technology Index (%)		
	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pool ed yield (No of Spikes/ha)	Pote ntial yield (No of Spikes/ha)	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25
T1: Farmers' practice –Arka Pratham	153750	155935	158125	155936.6	192700	-	-	-	38950	36765	34575	--	---	---	20.21	19.07	17.94
T2: Arka Amar	176250	184070	190875	183731.6	232422.4	14.634	18.042	20.711	56172.4	48352.4	41547.4	22500	28135	32750	24.16	20.80	17.87
T3: Arka Aayush	165000	170867.5	172875	169580.8	202412.5	7.317	9.576	9.328	37412.5	31545	29537.5	11250	14932.5	14750	18.48	15.58	14.59

Table 4. Economic analysis of gladiolus cultivation over farmers' practice

Particulars	Cost of Cultivation (Rs/ha)				Gross Returns (Rs/ha)				Net Returns (Rs/ha)				Cost Benefit Ratio			
	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pool ed	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pool ed	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pool ed	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25	Pooled
T1: Farmers' practice – Arka Pratham	824625	248637	251382	441548	922500	935610	948750	965120	97875	686972.5	697368	494071.8	1:1.11	1:2.76	1:2.77	2.21
T2: Arka Amar	824625	248637	251382	441548	1057500	1104420	1145250	1053484	232875	855783	893868	660842	1:1.28	1:3.44	1:3.55	2.75
T3: Arka Aayush	824625	248637	251382	441548	990000	1025202	1037250	1036890	165375	776565	785868	575936	1:1.20	1:3.12	1:3.12	2.48

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Fig. 1. Plant height gladiolus demo plots and farmers' practice

Fig. 2. Days to spike emergence in gladiolus demo plots and farmers' practice

Fig. 3. Pooled spike emergence of gladiolus varieties

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Fig. 4. Spike length of gladiolus demo plots and farmers' practice

Fig. 5. Pooled spike length of gladiolus varieties

Fig. 6 Spike vase life of gladiolus varieties

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Fig. 7 Number of florets per spike of gladiolus varieties

Fig. 8 Number of corms per plant of gladiolus varieties

Fig. 9 Number of spikes of Gladiolus varieties

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Fig. 10 Pooled spike yield of Gladiolus varieties

Fig. 11 Technology Gap in the cultivation of Gladiolus

Fig. 12 Technology Index (%) in the cultivation of Gladiolus

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Fig. 13. Cost of cultivation of Gladiolus

Fig. 14. Gross Returns of Gladiolus Cultivation

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Fig. 15. Net Returns of Gladiolus Cultivation

Fig. 16. Cost benefit ratios of Gladiolus Cultivation

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Gladiolus seed material

Seed treatment with Carbendizium and Mancozeb @ 5 g/kg of bulbs

Distribution of gladiolus seed material

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Main Field View of Gladiolus

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Judgement of gladiolus spikes: Opening of 2-3 florets from the base of spike

Arka Amar

Arka Aayush

Arka Pratham

Gladiolus spikes harvesting

Gladiolus spikes harvesting

Performance of Gladiolus Varieties Arka Amar and Arka Aayush in the Tribal Agency Areas of Alluri Sitaram Raj District of Andhra Pradesh

Bouque preparation with gladiolus spikes

Gladiolus bulbs harvesting